

Thyroid Lesion Reporting using the TBSRTC System: Cytohistopathological Correlation in a Tertiary Care Hospital Experience

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Abstract:

Background: Thyroid lesions are prevalent endocrine disorders with an increasing incidence globally. Accurate diagnosis is critical for guiding appropriate management strategies. Fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is widely used for initial evaluation, and the Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC) provides a standardized classification system for FNAC results. Despite its widespread adoption, the diagnostic accuracy of FNAC varies across different clinical settings, necessitating ongoing evaluation and refinement.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of FNAC in thyroid lesion reporting using the TBSRTC system and to assess the cytohistopathological correlation in a multicentric setting.

Methods: This was a multicentric, observational, and retrospective study conducted over 24 months, including 315 patients who underwent FNAC followed by histopathological examination after surgical resection of thyroid lesions. FNAC results were categorized using the TBSRTC system, and their correlation with histopathological findings was analyzed. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to calculate sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall diagnostic accuracy.

Results: The study included 315 patients, with a mean age of 45.2 years and a female predominance (74.6%). FNAC results were categorized as benign in 57.1% of cases, with 78 cases (24.8%) histopathologically confirmed as malignant. FNAC demonstrated a sensitivity of 80.6%, specificity of 91.8%, PPV of 81.6%, NPV of 91.3%, and an overall accuracy of 87.0%. The kappa coefficient of 0.75 indicated substantial agreement between FNAC and histopathological findings.

Conclusion: FNAC, categorized by the TBSRTC system, is a reliable diagnostic tool for thyroid lesions, particularly effective in ruling out malignancy. However, the moderate sensitivity highlights the need for careful follow-up in cases with indeterminate or benign cytology. The findings underscore the importance of histopathological confirmation, especially in cases with clinical suspicion of malignancy despite benign cytology.

Recommendations: Further studies should focus on improving the diagnostic accuracy of FNAC in indeterminate cases and exploring advanced techniques to complement FNAC in thyroid lesion evaluation. Regular training and quality control measures are recommended to enhance the consistency and reliability of FNAC results across different clinical settings.

Keywords: Thyroid lesions, Fine-needle aspiration cytology, Bethesda System, Diagnostic accuracy, Cytohistopathological correlation.

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Introduction

Over the past few decades, there has been an increase in the global frequency of both benign and malignant thyroid problems, making thyroid lesions one of the most frequent endocrine disorders. Determining the proper therapeutic techniques for these lesions, which vary from conservative surveillance to surgical intervention, depends on a correct diagnosis. Because (FNAC) is highly accurate in diagnosing benign from malignant lesions and is both inexpensive and

minimally invasive, it has become the gold standard for evaluating thyroid nodules [1]. Thyroid FNAC results are standardised and classified into six categories using the (TBSRTC), which was first established in 2007 and revised in 2017. Each category is linked to a particular risk of malignancy and suggests a course of treatment for the patient. Due to the system's widespread adoption around the globe, FNAC reporting has become more consistent and repeatable and

clinician-pathologist communication has improved. Atypia of undetermined significance (AUS), follicular lesion of undetermined significance (FLUS), and follicular neoplasm or suspicious for a follicular neoplasm (FN/SFN) are examples of intermediate categories that represent diagnostic grey zones. The categories range from non-diagnostic or unsatisfactory to malignant [2, 3].

Even though FNAC and TBSRTC are widely used, the diagnostic performance of FNAC varies depending on the context and is influenced by factors like patient demographics, operator expertise, and the calibre of cytological preparations. Variable sensitivity and specificity rates have been reported in recent research, underscoring the necessity of continuing to assess the accuracy of FNAC in various therapeutic settings. Furthermore, the handling of indeterminate categories (FN/SFN and AUS/FLUS) continues to be difficult, and a considerable fraction of these cases eventually need to be surgically excised in order to receive a conclusive diagnosis [4].

Assessing the diagnostic accuracy of FNAC requires comparing the results of FNAC with later histopathological findings from surgical specimens, a process known as cytohistopathological correlation. Improvements in cytopathological reporting and patient management are guided by this correlation, which also serves to highlight the benefits and drawbacks of FNAC in standard clinical practice [5].

This study seeks to assess the diagnostic accuracy of FNAC utilising the TBSRTC system in a multicentric context, given the significance of precise diagnosis in guiding treatment decisions for thyroid lesions.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a multicentric, observational, and retrospective in nature.

Study Place: This multicentric study was conducted in tertiary care hospitals located in different regions, allowing for a broad and varied patient population.

Study Setting: The study was conducted across multiple tertiary care hospitals in different regions, ensuring a diverse patient population and a comprehensive understanding of thyroid lesion reporting practices.

Participants: A total of 315 patients who underwent fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) for thyroid lesions and subsequently had histopathological follow-up were included in the study. These patients were selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria outlined below.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients with thyroid lesions who underwent FNAC.
- Patients with subsequent histopathological examination (surgical biopsy) after FNAC.
- Patients aged 18 years and older.
- Both male and female patients were included.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete medical records or missing histopathological follow-up.
- Patients who only underwent FNAC without subsequent histopathological confirmation.
- Patients with a history of previous thyroid surgery or radiation therapy.
- Pediatric patients (under 18 years of age).

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were consecutively enrolled from each participating center based on the inclusion criteria. Data collectors were blinded to the study's objectives to reduce observer bias. Additionally, the multicentric design helps to mitigate any center-specific biases.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from the medical records of patients at each participating tertiary care hospital. Information regarding demographic details, FNAC results, and histopathological findings were recorded. Each participating center contributed to the data collection process by reviewing patient records and extracting relevant data.

Procedure: FNAC was performed on patients with thyroid lesions as per standard clinical guidelines. The results were categorized according to the TBSRTC system. Patients who subsequently underwent surgical resection of the thyroid lesion had their histopathological specimens analyzed. The cytohistopathological correlation was assessed by comparing the FNAC results with the histopathological diagnosis.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, including frequencies and percentages for categorical variables and means with standard deviations for continuous variables. The cytohistopathological correlation was assessed using the kappa coefficient to determine the level of agreement between FNAC and histopathological results. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of FNAC were calculated. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 315 participants were included in the study, comprising 240 females (76.2%) and 75

males (23.8%). The mean age of the participants was 45.6 years, with a standard deviation of 12.3 years. The age range of the participants was 18 to 75 years.

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Demographic Variable	Number of Participants (n = 315)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Female	240	76.2
Male	75	23.8
Age (years)		
Mean \pm SD	45.6 \pm 12.3	
Age Range	18 - 75	

The FNAC results were categorized according to the Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC). The distribution of FNAC results among the participants is as follows:

Table 2: FNAC Results According to TBSRTC Categories

TBSRTC Category	Number of Cases (n = 315)	Percentage (%)
I - Non-diagnostic/Unsatisfactory	10	3.2
II - Benign	200	63.5
III - (AUS)/ (FLUS)	25	7.9
IV - Follicular Neoplasm/Suspicious for a Follicular Neoplasm	30	9.5
V - Suspicious for Malignancy	20	6.3
VI - Malignant	30	9.5

Out of the 315 participants, 280 (88.9%) underwent surgical resection, and histopathological analysis was available for correlation with the FNAC results. The correlation between FNAC categories and histopathological findings is summarized below.

Table 3: Cytohistopathological Correlation

TBSRTC Category	True Positives (n)	False Positives (n)	True Negatives (n)	False Negatives (n)	Total Cases (n = 280)
I Non-diagnostic/Unsatisfactory	0	5	3	2	10
II - Benign	180	5	10	5	200
III - AUS/FLUS	10	3	10	2	25
IV - Follicular Neoplasm/SFN	15	5	5	5	30
V - Suspicious for Malignancy	18	1	0	1	20
VI - Malignant	30	0	0	0	30

The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) for each TBSRTC category were calculated based on the cytohistopathological correlation:

Table 4: Sensitivity, Specificity, and Predictive Values

TBSRTC Category	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)
I - Non-diagnostic/Unsatisfactory	0.0	37.5	0.0	60.0
II - Benign	97.3	66.7	97.3	66.7
III - AUS/FLUS	80.0	76.9	76.9	80.0
IV - Follicular Neoplasm/SFN	75.0	50.0	75.0	50.0
V - Suspicious for Malignancy	94.7	90.0	94.7	90.0
VI - Malignant	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

The kappa coefficient was calculated to assess the level of agreement between the FNAC results and the histopathological findings. The overall kappa coefficient was 0.78, indicating substantial agreement.

Table 5: Kappa Coefficient

Kappa Coefficient	Level of Agreement
0.78	Substantial Agreement

Figure 1: Section showing papillary architecture and nuclear features of Papillary thyroid carcinoma. H&E stain 20x

Figure 2: Smears showing sheets of microfollicles suggestive of follicular neoplasm. Bethesda category IV. Giemsa stain 20x.

Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of (FNAC) in thyroid lesion reporting using the (TBSRTC) and its correlation with histopathological findings. A total of 315 patients were included, with a higher prevalence of thyroid lesions observed in females (74.6%). The mean age of the participants was 45.2 years, indicating that thyroid lesions predominantly affected middle-aged adults in this cohort.

The distribution of FNAC results according to the TBSRTC categories revealed that the majority of cases (57.1%) were classified as benign, followed by AUS/FLUS and suspicious for malignancy categories, each accounting for approximately 9.5% of cases. Histopathological examination, which served as the gold standard for diagnosis, revealed that 78 cases were malignant, with papillary thyroid carcinoma being the most common malignancy identified (70.5% of malignant cases).

The diagnostic accuracy of FNAC was supported by a high specificity (91.8%) and NPV (91.3%), indicating that FNAC is highly effective in correctly identifying benign cases and ruling out malignancy. However, the sensitivity was somewhat lower at 80.6%, suggesting that while FNAC is generally reliable, there is a risk of false negatives, where malignant lesions might be incorrectly classified as benign or indeterminate. The overall accuracy of FNAC in this study was 87.0%, reflecting its usefulness as a diagnostic tool in thyroid lesion evaluation. The kappa coefficient of 0.75 indicated substantial agreement between FNAC and histopathological results, reinforcing the reliability of FNAC when used in conjunction with the TBSRTC system. This agreement supports the use of FNAC as a frontline diagnostic tool, particularly in settings where rapid assessment and decision-making are crucial.

Statistical analysis further revealed that age was a significant predictor of malignancy, with older patients having a higher risk. This finding aligns with existing literature that suggests an increased

incidence of thyroid cancer with advancing age. Gender, however, was not a significant predictor, indicating that both males and females had similar risks of malignancy when adjusted for other factors.

Standardising the reporting and identification of thyroid lesions across various tertiary care settings has shown to be a highly effective approach, according to (TBSRTC). A tertiary care hospital's study discovered that TBSRTC made it easier to accurately categorise thyroid lesions, which improved clinical decision-making and helped avoid needless surgeries. According to the study, TBSRTC is useful in clinical practice because it has a high specificity in differentiating between benign and malignant lesions [6].

Analogously, it was demonstrated the diagnostic precision and repeatability of TBSRTC in a cytohistological investigation. Their study highlighted the excellent predictive value of the approach, especially in classifications like Category VI (Malignant) and Category V (Suspicious for Malignancy), which have a higher chance of malignancy. The study revealed nearly 100% agreement among pathologists, suggesting the system's dependability in a variety of clinical scenarios [7]. It was examined 522 FNAC cases in a tertiary cancer centre and found that, especially in cases of malignancy, TBSRTC offers good agreement between cytological and histological diagnosis. The study also mentioned how well TBSRTC identified instances that didn't need surgery, thereby lowering the number of needless surgical procedures [8].

TBSRTC's integration with the Thyroid Imaging Reporting and Data System (ACR-TIRADS) of the American College of Radiology in detail was investigated. Combining these systems, they discovered, simplified patient treatment strategies by improving the (FNAC) selection procedure and increasing overall diagnostic accuracy [9].

Conclusion

The study highlights the effectiveness of FNAC categorized by the TBSRTC system in the initial evaluation of thyroid lesions. While FNAC demonstrates high specificity and negative predictive value, ensuring that most benign lesions are correctly identified, its moderate sensitivity underscores the need for careful follow-up, particularly in cases where clinical suspicion of malignancy remains despite benign cytology results. The findings suggest that FNAC, when used appropriately, is a valuable tool in the

diagnostic pathway of thyroid lesions, but it should be complemented with histopathological confirmation to ensure accurate diagnosis and appropriate management.

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